

FARCLIMATE

DELIVERABLE D1.4 Ethical Issues Assessment

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List of acronyms

ALLEA: All European Academies

APA: American Psychological Association

DMP: Data Management Plan

EDI: Equity, Diversity and Inclusion

EU: European Union

FAIR: Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability

GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation

HSE: Health, Safety and Environment

IP: Intellectual Property

NGO: Non-Governmental Organisation

SME: Small and Medium Enterprise

UN: United Nations

WP: Work Package

Project information

Project full title: Moving ForwARd to achieving CLIMATE-resilient and sustainable European regional economic systems - FARCLIMATE

Acronym: FARCLIMATE

Call: HORIZON-MISS-2022-CLIMA-01

Topic: HORIZON-MISS-2022-CLIMA-01-04 - Transformation of regional economic systems for climate resilience and sustainability

Start date: 1st October 2023

Duration: 48 months

List of participants:

Partner No.	Organisation Name Acronym
1 (Coord.)	UNIVERSIDAD DE VIGO UVIGO
2	CONTACTICA S.L. CTA
3	INTERNATIONAL UNION FOR CONSERVATION OF NATURE UICN
4	C4G - CONSULTING AND TRAINING NETWORK, LDA C4G
5	INVIABLE LIFE CYCLE THINKING S.L. INV
6	MUNICIPIO DO FUNDAO FUNDAO
7	GREEN GROWTH GENERATION GGG
8	UNIVERSITY OF LIEGE ULIEGE
9	FUNDACIÓN CENTRO DE SERVICIOS Y PROMOCIÓN FORESTAL Y DE SU INDUSTRIA DE CASTILLA Y LEON CESEFOR
10	UNIVERSIDADE NOVA DE LISBOA UNL
11	FUNDACIÓN PARA LA PESCA Y MARISQUEO FUNDAMAR FUNDAMAR
12	EUROPEAN NETWORK OF LIVING LABS IVZW ENOLL
13	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS CERTH
14	LAUREA-AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY LAU

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1 Executive summary

The purpose of this deliverable is to give an overview of the ethical issues of the FARCLIMATE project and how they will be addressed. This document is elaborated within the context of task T1.4 (ethical issues assessment), which supports the FARCLIMATE consortium in assessing ethical issues and conducting the research and activities done in FARCLIMATE in an ethical manner.

In Section 2, after a brief introduction to the main ethical ideas of the deliverable, we briefly present the core legal foundations (EU regulations on Horizon Europe, GDPR, Open Data and the Grant Agreement) and ALLEA's four principles of research integrity (reliability, honesty, respect and integrity).

In Section 3, we conduct the assessment of the ethical issues. Namely:

- The ethical approach to participants in FARCLIMATE activities, including obtaining informed consent.
- The approach to protecting personal and other sensitive data (intellectual property or data from organisations) and to open data. This also includes the core ideas of integrating data protection and open data in the Data Management Plan.
- Accountability: robust methodology and clear roles and responsibilities.
- Non-EU Countries.
- Health, safety and environment.
- Diversity, equity and inclusion, including gender transformative programming.
- Environmental impact of FARCLIMATE results.

Section 4 presents how we will monitor ethical issues during the rest of the project.

Finally, Annex I provide a template for the information sheet and the informed consent.

2 Introduction

Ethics is a crucial aspect of research and innovation. It is essential to adhere to ethical norms to promote research integrity aims such as reliability, honesty, respect and accountability.

It is crucial to protect the rights of the people participating in the activities of FARCLIMATE and ensuring that their personal data is not misused. Informed consent is a critical component of ethical research, and it involves obtaining permission from participants after providing them with all the necessary information about the study, including its purpose, risks, and benefits. Protecting personal data in line with data protection regulations is another critical aspect of ethical research. The FARCLIMATE consortium must ensure that the data collected from participants is kept confidential and secure. Personal and other sensitive data should only be used for the purpose for which it was collected, not be disclosed to third parties without the participant's consent and protected, by keeping it confidential and secure. The project must also ensure that the goals of data protection and open data are integrated into the project's data management plan. Other key ethical aspects of FARCLIMATE are adherence to robust methodologies, clear roles and responsibilities and protection of health, safety and the environment.

Ensuring that research is inclusive and pays attention to diversity is also essential. An inclusive research approach, such as the one blended in FARCLIMATE, involves the participation of diverse groups, including those often marginalised or underrepresented. Inclusive research can ensure that all individuals' needs and perspectives are considered when developing innovations that help us adapt to climate change. It can also help build trust with participants. Furthermore, innovations that help us adapt to climate change must be developed ethically and inclusively, employing a gender transformative approach, to ensure they are effective and sustainable.

2.1 Legal foundation

The FARCLIMATE project will adhere to all applicable European and national laws and regulations, including any additional regulations that may be implemented during the project's development.

Specifically, we highlight the following legislation:

- Art. 19 of the **Regulation (EU) 2021/695 (Horizon Europe)**, which establishes the principle of proportionality, right to privacy, right to the protection of personal data, right to the physical and mental integrity of a person, right to non-discrimination and assurance of human health protection.
- Art. 14 of the **Grant Agreement** and Art. 14 of **Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement**.
- **Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR)**.
- **Directive (EU) 2019/1024 (Open Data and the Re-use of Public Sector Information)**.

2.2 General principles of research integrity

FARCLIMATE will ensure a solid commitment to the principles of **The Code of Conduct for Research Integrity of ALLEA** (All European Academies), which states that *"good research practices are based on fundamental principles of research integrity. They guide individuals, institutions, and organisations in their work as well as in their engagement with the practical, ethical, and intellectual challenges inherent in research"*. These principles include:

- **Reliability** in ensuring the quality of research.
- **Honesty** in research.
- **Respect** for colleagues, participants, society, culture and the environment.
- **Accountability** for the research.

Participants with their own internal codes of conduct in their organisations should also be apply them where appropriate.

3 Ethical issues assessment

3.1 Participants

A **participant** is a person who serves as a data source for research or participates in a project activity and whose personal information is obtained or used in that research or activity.

A key starting point of FARCLIMATE is the involvement of the stakeholders since the beginning of the project to make tailor-made plans and actions. Moreover, this will result in the implementation of several tailored living labs in the case studies, with the active involvement of the stakeholders.

Specifically, participants will be involved in FARCLIMATE as:

- Stakeholders of the case studies (set up as living labs), which involves participation in interviews and workshops for challenge identification and co-creation activities under a living lab methodology (WP2), as well as participating in workshops, evaluations and interviews for the case study analyses (WP3) and sector-specific innovations (WP5). Case study stakeholders will also participate in living lab, consumer, industry and business training (WP4) and user research workshops for designing the online platform (WP7). Workshops and interviews will be both face-to-face and virtual.
- Other participants in a consumer behaviour research survey (WP3). A survey will be developed and used for data collection and will be validated with experts in the mentioned topic and the whole consortium. The survey will include socio-demographic questions to characterise the sample. It is expected to collect at least 400 complete responses from each case study to guarantee representativity.
- Other participants in consumer, industry and business training (WP4). The training will take place both online and offline, and an educational platform will be launched to support learning.

In addition, ethics shall also be considered when dealing with other people concerned with the project activities, specifically:

- The audience of the dissemination and communication actions of FARCLIMATE (WP8).
- People contacted through FARCLIMATE's cooperation strategy with other EU projects, networks and institutions related to the EU Climate Adaptation Mission (WP8).
- People involved in the exploitation activities and intellectual property rights (WP8).

3.1.1 Ethical approach to participants

We strictly commit to the following ethical principles, set out in the ***Ethics in Social Science and Humanities Guidance Note (2021)***, for protecting human participants and ensuring they are treated fairly and with respect:

- Respect human dignity and integrity.
- Ensure honesty and transparency towards research subjects.
- Respect individual autonomy and the rights and interests of the participants.
- Obtain free and informed consent.
- Protect vulnerable individuals.
- Do not result in discriminatory practices or unfair treatment.
- Minimise harm and maximise benefit.
- Distribute benefits and burdens fairly.
- Ensure privacy and confidentiality (more details in Section 3.2).
- Promote justice and inclusiveness (more details in Section 3.6).
- Share the benefits with disadvantaged populations (more details in Section 3.6).
- Respect and protect the environment and future generations (more details in Section 3.7).

The key sources of these principles are the *Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union* and the *European Convention on Human Rights* and its Protocols, the *UN Declaration of Human Rights*, the *UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities* and widely accepted declarations that codify principles of research ethics and ethical treatment of research participants such as the *Nuremberg Code*, the *Helsinki Declaration* and the *Belmont Report*.

Our assessment establishes that the activities of FARCLIMATE do not entail more than minimal ethical risk. The research interaction with the participants does not pose the risk of inducing or involving psychological, medical, social, legal, economic or environmental harm.

3.1.2 Informed consent and information sheets

Article 4(11) of the *Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR)* states that "*'consent' of the data subject means any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her*". Additionally, it is also relevant the Article 2(2.21) of the *Regulation (EU) 536/2014 (on Clinical Trials)*, which states that "*'Informed consent' means a subject's free and voluntary expression of his or her willingness to participate in a particular clinical trial, after having been informed of all*

aspects of the clinical trial that are relevant to the subject's decision to participate or, in case of minors and of incapacitated subjects, an authorisation or agreement from their legally designated representative to include them in the clinical trial”.

Most of the participants will be able to give informed consent. Participation must be entirely voluntary, and informed consent must be obtained.

However, following the indications of the **EU Grants: ow to Complete your Ethics Self-Assessment V2.0 (2021)**, **should any activity involve participants who are unable to give informed consent** (e.g., dissemination or training activities with education centres), the consent must be obtained from the parents/legally authorised representative, and it must be ensured that they have sufficient information to provide authorisation on behalf and in the best interests of the persons unable to give consent. Whenever possible, the assent of the participants should be obtained in addition to the consent of the parents/legal representatives. Dissent should be respected. A brief justification for involving persons unable to give informed consent should also be provided.

Participants in FARCLIMATE activities must be given a project- or activity-specific informed consent form and information sheets that:

- Use a language and terms participants can fully understand.
- Describe the aims and implications of the activity and research methodology, the rationale of the participation and any risk and benefits that might arise.
- Inform about their right to privacy and confidentiality.
- State that participation is voluntary and that participants have the right to refuse to participate and to withdraw their participation or data at any time without any consequences.
- [If applicable] Include additional clauses to give consent to:
 - The use of images taken during the event in communication materials for the project.
 - The inclusion in a project information mailing list or newsletter.
 - Whether or not to agree to non-personal data being shared with others for future research.

FARCLIMATE partners must ensure that potential participants fully understand the information and do not feel pressured or coerced into giving consent.

Participants must normally give their consent in writing by signing the informed consent form and information sheets. Informed consent must also be obtained in advance of the activity.

Annex I provides a template for the information sheet and the informed consent.

Nonetheless, partners can use their own information sheets and informed consent forms if they comply with the principles stated here and GDPR and provide information about the FARCLIMATE project, the project logo and the funder's logos.

3.2 Data

3.2.1 Personal data

Personal data refers to information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person. Article 4(1) of *Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR)* states that *"'personal data' means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person"*.

Individuals are not considered 'identifiable' if identifying them requires excessive effort. Completely anonymised data do not fall under the data protection rules (as from the moment it has been completely anonymised, the GDPR is not applicable).

In activities where personal information is gathered and stored, FARCLIMATE partners must pay special attention to privacy, data protection and data management.

The consortium will collect common personal data, e.g., name and professional contact information, location or interviews. The use of personal data is envisaged for tasks dealing with stakeholder engagement, co-creation activities, living labs, workshops, consumer behavioural assessments, training, the creation of demonstrative stands and brigades, etc. In total, the use of personal data is envisaged in the following tasks:

- T2.2 Selection of case studies
- T2.3 Stakeholder management strategy
- T2.4 Set up of the case studies through living lab methodology
- T2.5 Fostering a transformative change to resilience environments
- T3.1 Integrated assessment framework
- T3.3 Social analysis and impact on wellbeing
- T3.4 Consumer behaviour and empowerment assessment
- T3.6 System climate innovation
- T4.2 Training coordination
- T4.3 Training deployment
- T4.4 Consumers-oriented and living lab training
- T4.5 Industry resilient solutions
- T4.6 Business resilient solutions
- T5.2 Innovations in Climate Resilient Agriculture
- T5.3 Closed to Nature silviculture management
- T5.4 European Network of Resilient to Climate Change Brigades in the fishing sector
- T7.1 User research and content strategy development
- T7.4 User experience assessment
- T8.2 Communication and dissemination actions
- T8.3 Cooperating with the EU and clustering activities

To comply with GDPR and national data protection laws, the processing of personal data in FARCLIMATE shall adhere to the following principles:

- Fairness
- Transparency
- Accountability
- Data quality
- Confidentiality
- Security

3.2.2 Other sensitive data

Intellectual property

FARCLIMATE intellectual property (IP) management follows the IAPED approach (identify, assess, protect, exploit, disseminate). At the proposal stage, FARCLIMATE identified the intellectual property interests of the consortium members and access rights within the project. During the project, the assessment and protection of intellectual property rights (IPR) will be addressed by task T8.4 (exploitation activities) and supervised by the Innovation and Exploitation Board (defined in D1.1 Project Management Guidelines).

Legal persons and organisations

Our activities also collect identifiable data of organisations.

3.2.3 Open data

As stated in the proposal, during and after the implementation of FARCLIMATE, the collected data and research outputs will be in line with the FAIR principles (findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability) and the **Directive (EU) 2019/1024 (Open data and the re-use of public sector information)**. This involves:

- Early and open sharing of research. E.g., preprints in open-access repositories.
- Measures to ensure the reproducibility of research outputs.
- Providing open access to research outputs, guided by the principle 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary'. At the latest (at publication time), the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication will be deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications to provide immediate open access.
- FARCLIMATE partners will deposit generated and collected data in an open online research data repository.
- At least 15 scientific publications relating to FARCLIMATE results are expected to be published (during the project and after it ends) in open access. After depositing publications, partners will ensure their open access via Green or Golden Open Access models.

3.2.4 Integrating data protection and open data in the Data Management Plan

Personal data collection, storage, modification, retrieval, transmission and elimination must be subject to appropriate safeguards. In addition, the level of data security must be appropriate to the risk for the participants in case of disclosure.

Whenever the consortium needs to process personal data, they will do so in compliance with applicable GDPR and national law on data protection (including authorisations or notification requirements). Art. 5 of the GDPR defines the following main principles regarding the processing of personal data: (a) lawfulness, fairness, and transparency; (b) purpose limitation; (c) data minimisation; (d) accuracy; (e) storage limitation; (f) integrity and confidentiality; and (g) accountability.

As such, **in addition to the FAIR principles to govern the open science data strategy of the project, the other major principles of FARCLIMATE Data Management Plan (DMP) concern security:** (1) confidentiality of personal and other sensitive data and (2) the integrity and availability of the data and information systems of the project.

Specifically, the key information systems managed by FARCLIMATE partners are:

- The common working space of the consortium in Teams (WP1).
- The website and dissemination/communication lists (WP8).
- The online platform: FARCLIMATE Transformation Hub (WP7).
- Online training platforms that may be used in WP4.
- Other information systems employed internally by the partners to collect, store or process data related to the project.

The DMP will set technological and procedural measures to ensure the security goals, including the confidentiality of personal and other sensitive data such as IP, in line with GDPR and national data protection laws. It will include information on: (1) procedures to collect, process and generate data; (2) methodology for standards; (3) data sharing; and (4) procedures for data archiving and preservation (during and after the project).

Consortium members must follow these measures. The partners collecting, storing and processing the data during their own activity will remain responsible for this data.

Regarding data quality and accessibility, there will be a curation and storage procedure. Documents generated during the project and raw and processed data will be retained in the project's repository after its ending, for a period of 5 years. During the project, data will be stored on the FARCLIMATE web-cloud and replicated to a separate external server. A user-friendly interface and clear rules on its accessibility will be guaranteed.

The initial DMP (D1.2) will be delivered in M6 of the project (March 2024). The DMP will be a live document that will be updated based on the project's progress and needs.

3.2.5 Use of personal data

Beyond the management of the datasets and information systems, the use of the personal data gathered in FARCLIMATE must commit to the following principles:

- Personal data must be used in accordance with the informed consent given by the participant and the rights they have regarding their data.
- Wherever possible, personal data must be processed anonymously or pseudonymously. Data and research outputs will be anonymised before being made accessible to third parties.
- Personal data must be processed only if it is genuinely adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for the project (data minimisation principle).
- Using personal data and images/video for communication purposes will require specific authorisation, documented in a specific clause in the informed consent form.

3.3 Accountability

3.3.1 Robust methodology

FARCLIMATE brings together leading experts of Knowledge Theory (UVIGO), Environmental Sciences (CTA), Forestry (CESEFOR), Agroecology (ULIEGE), Marketing and Business (UVIGO), Sustainability (UICN, CERTH, CTA), Political Sciences (UVIGO, FUNDAO), Computer Science (INV), Fishing Sciences (FUNDAMAR), Educational and Empowerment Sciences (C4G, UVIGO, GGG, ENoLL, CERTH, LAUREA), Living Labs (ENoLL, CERTH, LAUREA), Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CTA, ENoLL, CERTH, LAUREA), Data Visualisation (INV), Behavioural Sciences (UNL) and Gender Sciences (UICN & INV). This unique consortium has multidisciplinary and complementary backgrounds, knowledge and skills, and joins research institutions, SMEs, NGOs and public entities, making the FARCLIMATE consortium able to achieve the challenging objectives that have been set. The different partners are versed in the methodologies required for the living lab and stakeholder engagement activities of WP2, the research activities in WP3 and WP5, the training activities of WP4, the development of the online platform of WP7, the project management of WP1 and the dissemination, communication and exploitation activities of WP8.

The 20 case studies (WP2) are selected based on different documents, studies, and indexes (e.g., GCRI, CCPI) by internationally recognised organisations specialising in climate change. The selection is based on impact, vulnerability and adaptive capacity to climate change criteria. In addition, new criteria will be introduced to identify the regions or municipalities most affected by the consequences of climate change. For instance, the addition of a spatial criterion. This selection process will be described in deliverable D2.2 (due in M6, March 2024). After that, FARCLIMATE will recruit the different stakeholders, with the support of the primary liaisons of the different case studies, with the purpose of composing a diverse and inclusive group of stakeholders in each case study.

For the project, it is essential to engage stakeholders in creating solutions for climate change adaptation, which will be tailored to the specific contexts of each case study. FARCLIMATE will identify, support and train 20 communities – under the coordination of ENoLL and supported by CERTH and LAUREA – aiming for them to establish and grow into Certifiable Living Labs that foster co-creation and open innovation among the stakeholders.

3.3.2 Clear roles and responsibilities

Besides the general project management structures and protocols established in D1.1 Project Management Guidelines, it is essential to have clear roles and responsibilities for conducting research ethically and responsibly. Specifically:

- The project coordinator (UVIGO) is responsible for ensuring that the research and activities carried out in FARCLIMATE are conducted ethically and responsibly and that all partners are fully informed about the ethical implications of the activities.
- Consortium partners and their teams are responsible for carrying out the research or activities and adhering to the activity's accepted protocols. They are also responsible for ensuring that all participants in the activities are informed and treated with respect and for protecting the confidentiality and safety of all participants.
- Participants are responsible for providing honest and accurate information, following procedures and providing informed consent.

3.4 Non-EU countries

One partner of FARCLIMATE belongs to a non-EU country: UICN (Switzerland).

It is not planned to import or export anything but data between EU countries and Switzerland. Regarding this, the European Commission, on the basis of Art. 45 of *Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR)*, has determined that Switzerland has an adequate level of data protection (*Commission Decision 2000/518/EC* and reviewed in 2024 [*Document SWD (2024) 3 final*]) and, thus, personal data can flow from the EU to that third country without any further safeguard being necessary.

Additionally, the activities carried out by UICN (research and technical assistance in Nature-based solutions for agriculture, forestry and fishing) are allowed in other EU countries.

3.5 Health, safety and environment

The health and safety of all involved in FARCLIMATE are overriding priorities, as well as protecting the environment during our activities.

FARCLIMATE partners must commit to the following principles:

- Follow applicable EU and national laws for health and safety.
- Follow applicable EU and national legislation on nature conservation and pollution.
- Follow the organisational procedures for health, safety and environment (HSE) applicable to the activity. This means the procedures of the organisation responsible for the activity as well as the procedures of the organisation responsible for the premises or location that hosts the activities. This is especially relevant in fieldwork activities on the industrial, fishery, agricultural or silvicultural premises or fieldwork in the sea or land (especially in WP5, e.g., in the silviculture demonstrative stands of T5.3 and in the workshop on climate change brigades in the fishing sector of T5.4).
- Follow standard procedures and proceed with caution when conducting the activities themselves.

- If the activity poses HSE risks, set a safety check procedure and conduct a more in-depth risk assessment.
- Ultimately, the people responsible for the activity or in the field can fully assess HSE concerns and warn and advise project teams, staff and other participants. In some cases, the person responsible must remove staff and participants from dangerous situations.

The impact of FARCLIMATE results on the environment is assessed in 3.7.

3.6 Diversity, equity and inclusion

Diversity, equity, and inclusion are intertwined, and it is only in combination that they are effectively achieved.

These three principles will help FARCLIMATE to promote fairness and justice in the activities carried out in the work packages, in the local communities hosting the case studies and, by guiding FARCLIMATE results, in the European adaptation to climate change.

Diversity refers to who is represented in a group or organisation. E.g., gender, culture, age, physical ability, psychological, professional, religious diversity, socioeconomic status, nationality or language identities among many others. As the ***Equity, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) Framework of the American Psychological Association (APA)*** states, diversity involves representing social identity groups that correspond to differences in power and privilege and recognising that people have multiple identities with different salience in different contexts.

Equity refers to fair treatment and justice, so that norms, policies and practices in place ensure a fair outcome. While the classical interpretation of equality assumes that everyone should be treated the same, equity adjusts treatment accordingly to make the result fair. As the *APA EDI Framework* indicates, equity is about providing resources according to the needs of people, correcting inequities, giving decision-making authority and creating conditions for optimal outcomes for all members of society. In other words, the equity goal is to ensure that identity is not predictive of opportunities¹.

Inclusion refers to creating an organisational setting that enables full and meaningful participation in the organisation for all its members. An inclusive environment offers psychological safety and appreciation of different capabilities, perspectives and experiences, allowing all individuals to belong and participate in the organisation fully.

FARCLIMATE commits to being a diverse and inclusive project where people feel safe, respected and valued and where their voices are heard and considered. The living lab and stakeholder management methodologies of WP2 will be based on social and environmental sustainability criteria and will encourage inclusion and dialogue across cultures, disciplines, genders and ages. They will promote dialogue and co-creation among stakeholders in each region and community that will host a living lab (including small businesses, local authorities, trade unions, NGOs and local associations). There will be a dedicated focus on vulnerable groups (e.g., discriminated people, minorities, persons with disability). Living labs place citizens at the centre of innovation, demonstrating that they are powerful tools for developing

¹ [What is diversity, equity and inclusion?](#), McKinsey & Company, 2022

new concepts and solutions to the specific needs and aspirations of local contexts, cultures, and creativity potentials. This living lab approach ensures the inclusion of the rights and interests of the participants, ensuring the empowerment of the voices of stakeholders representing more disadvantaged groups. Expressly, inclusion in participation is incorporated explicitly in the WP2 stakeholder engagement strategy (T2.3) and living lab set-up (T2.4)

This emphasis on inclusiveness and participation will also be present in the interaction of case study stakeholders with WP3, WP4 and WP5 research, technical innovations and training. WP3 activities analyse climate adaptation strategies from social impact and consumer lenses, aiming to promote climate adaptation strategies that take care of more vulnerable or disadvantaged groups, thus promoting a more equitable climate adaptation. We specifically address the socioeconomic impact in T3.4 (e.g., effects on the labour market, wellbeing, inclusive work, the role of women) and the consumer perspective (T3.5). Training activities (WP4) also target different types of stakeholders to build capabilities and empower them to face climate change adaptation. The stakeholders participating in WP2 will also contribute to and review the sector-specific innovations to be developed in WP5.

Furthermore, based on the focus on inclusiveness, diversity and equity of the previous activities, the results sought by FARCLIMATE and specified in WP6 (business and management models, policy recommendations and the European Climate-Resilient Communities Network) and WP7 (Transformation Hub) will seek, in addition to the economic and technical aspects, a fair and inclusive adaptation to climate change.

Usually, economic approaches suggest choosing the most cost-effective projects. Still, ethical concerns imply that adaptation decision-making needs to account for both the net benefits and the impacts on equity. FARCLIMATE includes the stakeholder's vision from minute one. This will help in deciding the best options per case study, based on economic indicators but also on social situations and consumers' perspectives.

All of this in the context of our gender transformative program for the project (see below in Section 3.6.2) and our communicational strategy of WP8 (summarised in the lemma "we all together can work for a climate-resilient future") that reinforces an active, participatory and positive approach amenable for promoting diversity, inclusion and equity. In this sense, important dissemination and communication materials, as well as part of our training material, will be made accessible and in local languages.

Overall, we will seek the involvement of diverse participants without any unfair discrimination by age, disability, race, gender, sexual orientation, religion, belief or ideology, among other factors. Anyone involved in society must be heard and considered in climate change adaptation.

3.6.1 Bias

Bias is a point of concern, and specific care needs to be taken. However, the research conducted in WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5 is based on the inclusion of diverse stakeholders from various case studies in different countries (20), which will help reduce bias. Nevertheless, control of a balanced composition of stakeholder will be in place (e.g., type of stakeholder or professional, age, gender balance).

3.6.2 Gender transformative programming

As described in the FARCLIMATE proposal, although the project will focus on providing climate-resilient measures, the inner nature of current society, habits and production is strongly influenced by gender.

FARCLIMATE is strongly committed to challenging and transforming existing gender norms, roles, and power dynamics to achieve greater gender equality.. As part of WP1 (project management), task T1.5 will be devoted to implementing a gender transformative program. This will lead to an in-depth understanding of both genders' needs, behaviours and attitudes, and the influence of socioeconomic factors, and will help researchers question gender norms and stereotypes and rethink standards and reference models.

Based on learnings from existing gender-transformative adaptation programs, this task will ensure that all the project activities and influence will adopt and promote good practices that lead to gender transformation in the activities of the eight WP as well as in the 20 case studies of FARCLIMATE (e.g., stakeholder and user analysis, understanding gender and social norms, equal voices, representation, decision making, co-creation activities, gender-based KPIs). In addition, living lab methodologies will integrate principles and KPIs for gendered-innovative living labs (WP2), and training will have an equal representation from each gender (WP4).

3.7 Environmental impact of FARCLIMATE results

FARCLIMATE directly addresses the **EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change**, and also supports EU policies and global commitments such as the *Sustainable Development Goals*, the *COP 21 Paris Climate Agreement*, the *European Green Deal*, the *Farm2Fork Strategy* and *Rural Development Programmes*. It aims at accelerating the transformation to a climate-resilient future in European regions and communities.

WP3 and WP5 activities involve the study of solutions for the agricultural, fishery and forestry sectors. The core mission of the technical innovations in these three sectors is the respect and protection of the environment and future generations. The main approaches that FARCLIMATE will use for these technical innovations are sustainable and environmentally friendly strategies such as Nature-based solutions, Climate-resilient agricultural practices, Close-to-Nature silviculture and Resilient-to-Climate Change Brigades in the fishing sector. The partners responsible for these methodologies have conducted thorough risk assessments to mitigate potential hazards, ensuring that our activities are environmentally friendly and pose no threats to the well-being of participants or the broader ecosystem.

The technical solutions to be implemented in the fishery, agriculture and forestry sectors are consolidated approaches that FARCLIMATE pursues to implement in the local environments of the 20 case studies, with the necessary adaptations. UICN will review the specific actions developed in each case study to provide recommendations based on the Nature-based Solutions Standard for the specific agricultural, silviculture, and fishery innovations. Nonetheless, FARCLIMATE partners will follow the precautionary principle, which requires that where there is plausible scientific evidence for serious risks, we must prove that a new technology will not harm the environment.

4 Ethics monitoring

Ethics monitoring (T1.4) will be done in parallel with project management activities to continuously assess the ethical impact of the activities and solutions developed within the project and the potential future implementations and deployments based on them.

Ethics monitoring will be done in close coordination with the following related tasks:

- The management of ethical issues shall follow the procedures established in D1.1 for project monitoring (meetings, reporting) and risk management (for reporting ethical risks). The overall project management monitoring tools (T1.3) will facilitate identifying and reporting ethical issues. On the operational side, the monthly project follow-up meetings and the risk reporting template provided in D1.1 will help us check potential ethical issues every month or when a partner identifies a relevant ethical issue, respectively.
- On a more strategic level, the General Assembly, Steering Committee and Innovation and Exploitation Board meetings may also help identify ethical issues. Nonetheless, the General Assembly will maintain an overview of the work throughout the project and help identify possible ethical issues that might arise and how they can be addressed.
- Data management activities (T1.2) are closely related to protecting personal data and compliance with GDPR, as well as with open data. As such, as partners identify new or modified datasets, they may also report any new or altered ethical implications if they arise (specifically, those related to personal data protection).
- The gender transformation programming (T1.5) and the stakeholder management activities of tasks T2.3 and T2.4 will also help to raise awareness of potential issues regarding diversity, equity, inclusion and gender.
- Should a new or altered ethical issue arise, the project coordinator (UVIGO) will review the ethical issue with the partners involved. If the issue is relevant for the rest of the consortium, the project coordinator will produce an internal report including suggestions and guidelines to ensure ethical compliance.

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Annexes

Annex I: Information sheet and informed consent templates

Please edit the fields marked in grey to adapt them to your activity/study/event. Feel free to translate the templates to local languages.

Information Sheet

Activity/Study/Event title

Write the title of the activity/study/event

Organiser of the activity/study/event

Write the name of the FARCLIMATE partner(s) organising the activity/study/event

Project information

Moving ForwARd to achieving CLIMATE-resilient and sustainable European regional economic systems – **FARCLIMATE**

FARCLIMATE will address the critical challenges of developing and expanding climate-resilient measures, making them available and understandable to everyone, while also paying particular attention to the social, political and economic barriers that are commonly found. FARCLIMATE actions will be implemented in at least 20 regions and communities in Europe, i.e., case studies where we will address transformative solutions on the path to climate resilience and adaptation to climate change.

This project has received funding under the European Union's HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions under Grant Agreement No. 101112860 and from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

Purpose of the activity/study/event

Briefly explain the purpose of the activity/study/event and its purpose within the FARCLIMATE project (e.g., task, deliverable).

Participation

Explain how participants were selected, the type of participation required from the participant, the participation procedure, duration, etc.

Risks

Explain the risks of participating in the activity/study/event for the participant.

Benefits

Explain the benefits of participating in the activity/study/event for the participant.

Responsibilities

As a participant, you are responsible for (1) providing honest and accurate information, (2) following procedures and (3) providing informed consent.

Recording

Explain how the data will be recorded (e.g., notes, photos, audio, video).

Sharing the results

We may share the research findings obtained from your data through publications and events. We may share the data we collect from you for reuse in future research studies, with other researchers or in open-data repositories. If we share the data, we will remove any personal information before we share it. Only anonymised data will be shared.

Explain further details if they apply to the activity/study/event

Protection of personal data

Your personal data will be handled as confidentially and securely as possible. All partner institutions involved in the FARCLIMATE project adhere to the European Union Regulation 2016/679 on General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and national data protection regulations.

We will collect only personal data that we need for the purposes of the described activity/study/event. Your personal data will be retained for as long as it is necessary to fulfil the purposes for which it has been collected, and in any case, no longer than the duration of the FARCLIMATE Project. Afterwards, your personal data will be permanently deleted. You have the right to be forgotten and remove any data provided at any time. You have the right to request access to your personal information. You have the right to rectify the personal information we hold about you.

Right of Withdraw

Participation in this study is voluntary. You do not have to answer any question you do not want to answer. If at any time and for any reason, you can withdraw from this study at any time, without any penalty or prejudice. It is possible to take a break, stop and continue later or stop altogether. You may withdraw from this study at any time.

Contact

For more information, visit the FARCLIMATE website (<http://project-farclimate.eu>)

If you have any questions, you can always contact:

- *Name of a responsible for this event/activity/study and email*
- Project coordinator of FARCLIMATE, Roberto Chico, roberto.chico.tato@uvigo.gal

Participant Consent Form

Please complete this form after you have read the Information Sheet about the activity/study/event.

Please place an "X in the boxes" to affirmatively consent to the following statements.

I was given the "Information Sheet", which explains to me, in writing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the purpose of the FARCLIMATE project, • the purpose of this activity/study/event and how it will be carried out, and • what my participation involves. 	
My questions about the activity have been answered to my satisfaction and I understand that I may ask further questions at any point.	
I am participating voluntarily and agree to participate in the activity/study/event.	
I understand that I can withdraw from the activities at any time without any penalty or prejudice.	
I consent to the processing of my personal data, and I am fully aware of my rights in accordance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (Reg. 2016/679).	
I understand that my personal data will be treated as strictly confidential and handled in accordance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (Reg. 2016/679).	
[If applicable] I consent to having research notes taken or recorded for activity/study/event purposes.	
[If applicable] I consent to having photos or videos taken of me for communication/dissemination purposes.	
I would like to receive updates on the progress and findings of the project.	
I agree that other researchers may use my non-personal data for future research.	

Please confirm your agreement by signing this form:

Name of the participant:

Signature of the participant:

Email of the participant:

Date: